

**METHODS AND AGROTECHNIQUES OF GROWING POLY CROPS
(MELON, PUMPKIN) IN THE SOIL CLIMATE CONDITIONS OF THE
REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAGISTAN**

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Abstract.

In this article, based on the needs of the population in our country, we will talk about the methods of growing melons, processing and drying measures.

Key words.

fruit products, melon, cultivation, technology.

Introduction

Climatic and geographical features of Uzbekistan, rare ecosystems containing unique species of flora and fauna, which are of great importance for the global ecological system of the planet, give reason to include the issues of ensuring environmental stability among national priority issues. Taking into account the high growth rates of the economy in Uzbekistan in recent years, it is recognized the need to alternate environmental protection actions with measures aimed at ensuring economic growth, including the rational use of natural resources and their preservation for future generations. UNDP contributes to achieving sustainable development by implementing programs and projects aimed at improving the institutional capacity of developing countries, as well as relevant pilot initiatives. At the end of 2015, at the 21st conference of all Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change held in Paris, combating threats and solving climate change-related problems in terms of reaching a global agreement on climate change became one of the priorities of further activities in this regard.

Literature Analysis And Methodology

The climatic conditions of Karakalpakstan are very favorable for the development of greenhouse vegetables. Because the intensive and long-lasting flow of solar radiation makes it possible to grow sab plant crops here throughout the year and in relatively short (3.5-4 months) heated seasons. Because of this, growing vegetables in greenhouses in this region is one of the useful directions of economic activity that ensures their production in the cold periods of the year. This, in turn,

makes it possible to improve the quality of nutrition of the population and increase the income of farmers, peasants and private households. Unfortunately, these opportunities are rarely used in the region. The area of greenhouses here is not large, and their productivity is very low. The low productivity of vegetables grown in greenhouses is explained by the violation of technological processes due to the low amount of organic matter in the soil, its salinity, the strong spread of pests and diseases, and the lack of practical recommendations that take into account the characteristics of local conditions. This Recommendation Guide was prepared in order to help farmers, peasants and owners of private plots of land with greenhouses in the northern districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, to master the full technological processes that ensure that they achieve guaranteed high productivity in growing vegetables in greenhouses throughout the year. The article covers the preparation of greenhouses for operation, soil processing, and technologies for growing vegetables in soil greenhouses, taking into account the characteristics of local conditions.

Biological characteristics and varieties. Cultivation of melons and watermelons in greenhouses is becoming widespread in many countries of the world. In melon, female buds appear under the bands of leaves on the second and third order lateral branches, in most cases, in one piece. Therefore, it is effective to hang them on sleepers. In watermelon, female flowers are mainly formed on the main stem. Therefore, there is no need to hang them. Flowering of watermelons and melons begins 25-35 days after they are set. At first, male buds will bloom, and after 5-10 days, female buds will bloom. After that, the flowering of male and female buds continues. Watermelon takes 45-54 days from germination to flowering, and 25-42 days from flowering to ripening. In melon, these processes are 35-43 days and 38-54 days, respectively. The main requirements for the cultivation of polys crops in greenhouses are as follows: high yield, quick ripening due to the ability to form female flowers in the lower joints, reduced light, sharp temperature changes, high humidity and resistance to fungal diseases, high taste of the product and its high quality in the commodity state, etc. . In Uzbekistan, melons are grown in greenhouses using handalak and summer soft varieties, which are one of its manifestations. Their regionalized varieties include Rohat, Handalak, Kokcha 14, Assata 3806, and non-regionalized varieties include Davlatboy local variety, Iliy Kazakh variety, Ogen and Zinger Dutch varieties. In the cultivation of watermelons in greenhouses, hybrids of Dutch varieties such as Krisby and Trofi, American hybrid Crimson Sweet, and local varieties of Orinboy and Surkhan Tongi are mostly used. Production technology. Some varieties of melons and watermelons

are planted in open ground in Uzbekistan. Their harvest lasts until April. Therefore, it is advisable to grow melons and watermelons in greenhouses in May-June. Because during this period, the crop does not ripen in the open ground. It is better to start the ripening of oleander crops in the heated greenhouses at the QR when the light starts to increase, that is, at the end of February. It is necessary to start work in this regard in mid-March in greenhouses that are heated only during spring, when the temperature drops sharply, and in the last five days of March in unheated greenhouses. Sometimes, the seeds are sown in the soil itself in the greenhouse. This event starts a week and a half ago. When growing melons and watermelons in a greenhouse, their 25-30-day-old seedlings are planted. These seedlings are grown in 10x10x10 cm containers with manure humus. The technology of preparing seedlings of polys crops is the same as preparing cucumber seedlings. When seedlings are planted in winter greenhouses during these periods, the first harvest of melons ripens at the end of April, and watermelons ripen at the beginning of May. In spring greenhouses, melons ripen in early May, and watermelons ripen in mid-May. In the cultivation of melons and watermelons, if their seeds are sown, the ripening of the crop is delayed by 10-15 days. In greenhouses, polys crops are placed in rows. In glass greenhouses, the capacity is 1.4-1.6 m x 30-70 cm, that is, 1.5-2.0 melon plants and 0.5-1 watermelon plants per 1 m² of surface. In film greenhouses designed for short vegetation, the plants are slightly denser, that is, in 70x70 cm and 80x40-45 cm schemes, 2-3 seedlings are placed on 1 m² of surface. In the first two irrigations, water is applied to each furrow, and in the subsequent ones, one furrow is watered. In this case, seedlings are grown in sizes of 70+70 and 80+80 cm, placed according to the scheme of the ribbon. Before planting seedlings, the soil in the greenhouse should be well worked. Mineral fertilizers are not added to polys crops. However, soil mixtures rich in organic matter and fertile are widely used in feeding them. Before transplanting a seedling, it should have two to three, but no more than four true leaves, oday, pumpkin seeds are actively planted in all parts of our Republic, and unique methods are used in each region. Here it is possible to plant pumpkins not by sowing seeds, but by seedlings. In this case, 6,000 pumpkin seedlings are planted on 1 hectare of land, 20 kg of harvest is obtained from one pumpkin seedling.

In order to get a good harvest from the pumpkin crop, it is necessary to plant high-quality, pure seeds. Pumpkin seeds that have been stored for one year, free from pests and fungi, will give the highest yield. Although seeds stored for 4-5 years retain their fertility, their productivity may decrease sharply.

Sowing of seeds is carried out from April 1 to April 10 in the southern regions, from April 10 to April 20 in the central regions, and from April 25 to May 10 in the northern regions. Care starts with weed control and replanting the seedling bug. Seedlings are divided twice, in which the first one leaves 2-3 plants in each nest when 1-2 leaves appear, and the second one leaves 1-2 plants in each nest when 3-4 leaves appear. The pumpkin is watered from 3-4 to 6-7 times depending on the depth of underground seepage. During the growth period, it is watered once after the first and second cut, then every 10-14 days until the fruit ripens, and every 15-20 days during the fruit ripening period. As these methods are effective in practice, farmers and peasants aim to raise higher yields and increase their incomes. Pumpkin fruit contains 10-15% dry matter, of which 4-11% is sugar. In addition, it contains 0.7% fiber, 0.5% protein, 0.2% oil, 0.6% ash, a large amount of mineral salts and vitamins. Pumpkin fruit is a cure for atherosclerosis, liver, kidney, stomach, and heart diseases, and the decoction of seeds has the property of expelling worms.

The pumpkin plant grown in Uzbekistan consists of three types: large-fruited, hard-skinned and nutmeg pumpkins. The structure of the stem is round in large-fruited pumpkins, 5-sided in hard-skinned pumpkins, and deeply carved with five sides in nutmeg pumpkins. The pumpkin root system is strongly developed. The length of the arrow root is 2 meters. The lateral roots of the first order are 2-5 meters long, 10-12 in number. Flowers on pumpkin bushes differ from each other in terms of their shape, color and other characteristics. The flower crown of the large-fruited pumpkin is the largest and lightest in color, while the flowers of the nutmeg pumpkin are the smallest. The petals of the large fruit gourd are turned outwards and have a hard skin, while the petals of the nutmeg gourd are upright and have a sharp tip. The calyx of the large-fruited gourd flower is cup-shaped, barrel-shaped, the calyx leaves are threadlike in the large-fruited gourd, thin, elongated in the nutmeg gourd, and lanceolate in the hard-skinned gourd. There are many similarities in the structure of different types of pumpkin flowers. Cauliflower has five members, the flower crown is bell-shaped, joined with the calyx, divided into 5 yellow or golden-colored leaves in the middle. Anthers of male flowers are folded like an anther and joined with each other, divided into 5 yellow or golden leaves in the middle. Pollen grains of male flowers are bent like a bow and joined together to form a single column. The diameter of the dust grains is 101-107 microns in the Spanish 73 variety, 106-111 microns in the Palov kadi variety. Female flowers have 3-5 pointed beaks with a thickened column, rounded or pointed, horseshoe-shaped. The node is lower and consists of three, sometimes 4-5 fruit leaves. The internal

cavity of the pumpkin fruit contains the placenta and seeds. There is a cold layer in the skin, this layer is the most mature in hard-skinned pumpkins.

Results

Its place is prepared 5-7 days before planting. Seedlings are planted in conditions where the soil temperature is not lower than 14 0 C. Before planting seedlings, their place is marked on the surface of the soil in the greenhouse, according to the accepted planting scheme of the plant. Pits are dug in the places where seedlings are planted, and manure humus mixed with soil is placed at the bottom of them. The pits are moistened with 1.5-2.0 liters of water. As soon as the water dries up, plants are placed in the pit, and it is buried with soil up to a height of 1.5-2.0 cm from the surface of the earth. A lump is formed around the plant. After the seedlings are planted, they are watered from the furrows. Polys crops are grown in greenhouses on vertical slats. Each plant is tied with hemp twine. Later, the end of the plant stem is wrapped in hemp thread in a continuous process. Rohat melon and Orinboy tezpishar hybrids of watermelon almost do not branch. In other tezpishar varieties, two lateral branches (bach kilar of the 1st order) are removed. Because in most cases female buds appear late in them. The next three or four bachki are spread on the surface of the soil. Each of them, after the formation of buds of the female type, is pulled from 2-3 joints to the slats. Branches that have not formed female buds up to 6-7 joints of the plant are removed. The central stem of the plant is not hanging. The side branches of the first order in the middle and upper stages are hung on hooks from the parts after the 2-3 leaves of which the buds of the female type are formed. Standardization of joints accelerates the formation of early crops and improves their appearance and taste as a commodity. 4-5 fruit tubes weighing 0.8-1.2 g per plant are the norm. Harvest tubes are placed in net bags and hung on the upper wires of the sleepers or on the greenhouse hooks. The lower joints are formed, and pieces of plastic are placed under the melon crop above the soil (Fig. 4.3.1). Caring for polys crops grown in greenhouses includes maintaining the optimal temperature (26-28 0 C during the day, 18-20 0 C in the evenings), relative air humidity (60-70%). These conditions are achieved as a result of managing the heating and ventilation system, as well as timely implementation of watering and feeding, loosening the soil and effective control of pests and diseases. Irrigations are carried out at first moderately, and then in excess. During the growing season, the plant is watered through furrows. In greenhouse conditions, melons are watered 8-10 times per season, and watermelons are watered 1-2 times less. The soil is loosened 2-3 times. The plant is fed 1-2 times until the first crop is formed. Feeding composition and rate per 1 m² of surface: 15

g of ammonium nitrate, 30 g of ammophos and 10 g of potassium salt for melon; and for watermelon, it is 10, 30 and 30 g, respectively. Fertilization is carried out along with loosening the soil and watering. Fertilizer is applied by hand and buried in the soil. Crops of polys crops do not ripen at the same time. Therefore, their crops are harvested 3-4 times.

More than 160 varieties of melons can be found in the crops of the Republic of Uzbekistan, but most of them are planted in small areas. As of 2000, 33 varieties are regionalized in our republic, of which only the local Gurbek variety belongs to the Asia Minor subspecies, and the rest belong to the Central Asian subspecies. According to the duration of the growing season, melon varieties are divided into the following groups: 1. Early varieties (65-80 days pass from the appearance of the grass to the ripening of the first fruit). 2. Medium varieties (growing period 81-110 days). 3. Late ripening varieties (growing period more than 110 days). Out of the 33 varieties of melons regionalized in our country, 9 are early varieties, 14 are medium-ripening, and 10 are late-ripening. among medium-ripe melons - soft summer and hard summer melon varieties; among the late-ripening varieties, there are autumn and winter melon varieties. (Table 1). There are more than 20 varieties of watermelons in Uzbekistan, 12 of which are regionalized. According to the length of the growing season, watermelon varieties are divided into the following groups: 1. Early (up to 85 days pass from the germination of the grass to the ripening of the first fruit). 2. Mid-season (growing period 85-110 days). 3. Late (growing season 110 days and more) Watermelon varieties regionalized in our country can be divided into 3 groups according to the length of the growing season: early varieties - Orinboy, Olmos, Local Mozaichniy, Uzbek - 452; Medium varieties - Korol Kubi - 92, Mramorniy, Dilnoz, Neobichniy, Sputnik; late varieties - Ko'zivoi 30, Hayit - black, Gulistan. The Republic of Uzbekistan has various varieties of pumpkin. More than 140 varieties of pumpkins are found in collective, peasant farms and private plots, of which 40-45% are nutmeg pumpkins, 30-35% large-fruited pumpkins, and 25-30% hard-skinned pumpkins. Only 4 varieties are regionalized in our republic. Of these, Kashkar 1644 and Palav kadi 268 varieties belong to muscat pumpkins. The Spanish 73 variety belongs to the large-fruited pumpkins, and the Nonkadi variety belongs to the hard-skinned pumpkins. The Spanish 73 variety is considered to be a late bloomer with a growing period of 120-130 days, and other varieties are medium blooming with a growing period of 110-120 days.

Conclusion

Today, the importance of melon is very high, and the demand for ready-made dried melon products is increasing among the population of our republic. Based on this demand, scientific research is being carried out with the aim of producing products that are affordable for the population, that can be found on the market shelves throughout the year, in any season, and according to the demand of the population, using new innovative technologies.

Since the soils of Uzbekistan are well supplied with potassium, the use of nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers is of great importance. The requirement of polys crops for mineral nutrition is different at different stages of the growth period, which depends on the activity of the growth process. At the beginning of the growing season, the growth rate is slow, so mineral substances are not absorbed. As a result of the intensive growth of the vegetative and generative parts of plants, the assimilation of nutrients accelerates, and at the end of the growth period, it slows down again.

Organic fertilizers (manure) also have a good effect on the growth of rice crops. It is advisable to use organic and mineral fertilizers in the necessary quantities to obtain a high yield from field crops.

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